

Partnering with Industry for Authentic Assessment: Making our Graduates Workplace Ready.

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Traditional HE assessment, with its emphasis on conventional exams, encourages students to rely on surface-level learning and memorising information for a specific event. While these approaches have their place in HE settings, they deliver little impact on lifelong learning, and so it is widely accepted that assessments need to evolve to examples that are more authentic to the work-place.

What is authentic assessment?

Conversations on authentic assessment first came about in 1989 when Grant Wiggins wrote about it in his book, *A true test: toward more authentic and equitable assessment*. Authentic assessment requires students to complete assignments that mirror tasks carried out by professionals in employment. These tasks, therefore, command a deeper level of learning and help enhance students' career prospects.

With transferrable skills such as communication, critical thinking and problem-solving being highly valued by employers irrespective of graduate destinations, authentic assessment provides HE students with valuable opportunities to develop and evidence their professional skills. Embedding authentic assessment from the start of a course allows students to practice and refine their skills before entering the workplace. Such contextualised learning experiences can also have a positive impact on student motivation and engagement as they allow students to be able to see how their learning maps to their career goals.

Getting industry involved

External analyses and obligations to meet QAA benchmark statements that include expectations of professional behaviours, conduct and competencies mean that all university courses have increasingly placed more focus on producing graduates that can transition smoothly into employment. To use bioscience, as example, related courses develop a wide range of skills, meaning that these graduates can consider a diverse array of jobs and careers. Some graduates will move into roles in commercial ("for-profit") industry, but many will move into not-for-profit organisations, the healthcare sector, research institutes and educational institutions. It is also clear that bioscience graduates are attractive to organisations outside of the subject area and

that many graduates will try volunteering (unpaid) opportunities. This means that it is difficult to define the typical employer or “industry” for these courses.

Invite professionals to speak at your institution.

Collaboration with industry partners provides an effective way to introduce authentic assessment strategies into the curriculum. This may take many forms throughout modules and courses, but one productive approach is to enable students to interact with the partners. This can be through meet and greets or invited speaker talks where the employer representative can explain what their organisation does, helping students gain a wider appreciation of the skills they need to work in that industry. Showcasing work undertaken in the final year of courses, such as capstone projects, gives employers sight of the highest levels of skills and experiences gained by students, but there are also opportunities for them to engage earlier in the curriculum, such as with preparation for placements and the like. For such interactions, reach out to alumni who can highlight the skills they have made most use of in their careers and provide advice to students.

Organise student visits to places of work.

Giving students the opportunity to visit industry organisations immerses in the kinds of environments they may end up working in in the future and equips them with first-hand knowledge of what their career might look like. These workplace visits can be facilitated through communication with alumni via platforms such as LinkedIn or through pre-existing professional relationships. In other cases, they may come about through networking with industry professionals at conferences or online. As examples, effective opportunities for biomedical or microbiology students include visits to diagnostic laboratories and for ecology students, field trips to conservation sites and areas of scientific interest.

Opening a dialogue between industry and your institution

Building a relationship with industry partners requires a two-way dialogue, allowing partners to have direct input into the curriculum content and types of assessments to reflect real-world practices and develop more appropriate skills for such careers. This enhances curriculums, ensuring that the module and course level design is current and responsive to industry needs. Likewise, industry partners also gain benefits from interactions with institutions through discussion of graduate skills gaps, how best to prepare students to become workplace ready and how industries are evolving.

Nottingham Trent University and the University of East Anglia have both established an Employability Advisory Board (EAB) with representatives from a spectrum of bioscience career sectors. Board meetings are usually annual or biannual and have been successful both in-person and online. Online meetings are particularly useful if members are from national and international industries. Boards can be set up by reaching out to contacts who you already have an established relationship with or by asking colleagues if they have contacts in particular career sectors. Attending

conferences can provide opportunities to speak to new people and potentially grow your network. Building alumni networks using professional sites such as LinkedIn is a great way of generating a pool of individuals who you can open a new line of communication with. Successful alumni have a strong feeling of goodwill to the university and are likely to engage with opportunities at an earlier stage in their career, and make such activities part of an ongoing relationship, which may be easier than starting a relationship from scratch. They also have the advantage of a compelling narrative to pass on to students of how their degree links to their career. Reaching out for the first time to invite a potential new board member can feel daunting but remember, the recipient may feel very flattered to have been asked to represent their industry. In some cases it may be that they cannot commit but they know a colleague who would be interested, and so the network grows.

Integrate work experience into course design.

Another effective approach to authentic assessment is to integrate placements into modules or courses. Time commitments can range from a few hours to a few days to a full academic year. Although placements are useful, bear in mind that marking assessments associated with these will require significant involvement from academic staff. However, the immersion into an environment with very different priorities, rules and expectations builds professional attributes that are difficult to recreate within a HE setting.

By working with industry to produce activities reflecting the myriad of challenges professionals face in the workplace, it is possible to produce assignments that are less about essays and rote learning and more about the application of skills or real data and solving real-world problems.

Getting our students workplace ready is a challenge. However, having industry partners contributing to the curriculum can assist us in providing authentic experiences and assessments that will enhance transferable skills acquisition and equip our students for a successful future in their place of work.

1. Wiggins, G. (1989). *A true test: Toward more authentic and equitable assessment. Phi Delta Kappan*, 70(9), 703–713.